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Panda, Subhajit; Sinhababu, Dr. Atasi; and Chakravarty, Prof. Rupak, "Analysis of Global Published Literature on Library and Information Science: an Empirical Study through Big Data Approach (1920-2020)" (2021). *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. 6778.

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Analysis of Global Published Literature on Library and Information Science: an Empirical Study through Big Data Approach (1920-2020)

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Abstract

The purpose of this paper is to investigate the extent of LIS (Library and Information Science) literature referring to and being referred by patents in the form of scholarly citations they attribute and/or receive. The analysis of the present study was done based on a total data-set of 237820 research publications of the LIS discipline ranging from April 1920 to April 2020 (100 years) as mined from the LENS database. LIS research corpus received 22.75 scholarly citations and 6.87 patent citations per paper while utilizing and citing 18667 patents and thus establishing the correlation between the citing-cited link in the research ecosystem. In addition, this paper also evaluates the decadal Relative Growth Rate (RGR) and Doubling Time (D_t) of LIS publications ranging from May 1920 to April 2020. The paper reflects the value of LIS research in patents and vice versa depicting the cross-disciplinary nature and decadal growth rate of LIS in general and information science in particular.

Keywords: Lens, Scientometric, Library and Information Science, Citations, Patents

1. Introduction

Earlier, the publications were considered as the last milestone or step in the scholarly communication cycle but with the availability of highly functional and open platforms like ResearchGate, Mendeley and the Lens, researchers have now realized that there are unexplored horizons yet to be harnessed to the benefits of them only. These add-on services/tools are built on the top the infrastructure facilitated by the SCNs/ASCs leverage the findings of the research along with other important dimensions of the study like research data to make available an open system for extending and strengthening the already existing scholarly communication cycle. The scientometric study is a quantitative analysis of written communication and plays a vital role in the process of information research by showing that all the pieces of published information do not have equal importance (Chaman, Dharani and Biradar, 2017). The major focus of the present study is to apply the scientometric analysis with a view of analysing the performance & growth of global research output on Library and Information Science, its applications, citation count, journal coverage, authorship pattern and, in particular, its use in global patents; depending upon the data exported from the Lens.

2. Review of Related Literature

Various studies in library and information science based on research productivity have focused on the number of publications and their growth over time and ranking by countries, institutions, schools, authors and journals. Asubiaro and Badmus (2020) investigated the trends in the scope and subject classifications of Web of Science indexed library and information science research from authors that are affiliated with institutions in Africa between the time period 2006-2015. Javed & Liu (2017) aimed to forecast the research output of four selected countries (USA, China, India and Pakistan) using two models of Grey System Theory—Even Model GM (1,1) and Nonhomogeneous Discrete Grey Model (NDGM) and additionally studied publication growth analysis using relative growth rate and the doubling time. MT Basavraja, RS Vinay and Kori (2019) in the study “Trends in Library and Information Science Research: A Scientometric Analysis” aimed to investigate the authorship pattern, collaboration trends and growth of LIS research. Gupta and Dhawan (2019) examined the quantitative and qualitative description of global research on the topic of the “electronic books” published during 1993-2018 based on the selected bibliometric indicator. Kousha and Thelwall (2017) in the paper “Patent citation analysis with Google” illustrated how citations from patents to scientific publications (1996-2012) provide valuable evidence of the commercial influences of academic research and the findings indicated a weak positive correlation between Google Patent citations and Scopus citations. Suradkar and Khaparde (2012) did a scientometric analysis on the subject Library Management based on 11 volumes of LISTA (2000-2009), also additionally examined the mean for doubling time for the first five years. Yoshikane, Suzuki, and Tsuji (2012) examined and clarified the relationship between the diversity of classifications assigned to backward citations and the number of forwarding citations for Japanese patents. Garg and Padhi (1998) analyze in the paper “Scientometric study of laser patent literature” the patents filed and scientific papers published and abstracted in the Journal of Current Laser Abstracts (JCLA) for the period 1967–95. The purpose of the paper of Maharana, Nayak, and Sahu (2006) was to measure the number of web resources used for scholarly contributions in the area of library and information science (LIS) in India; which aimed to analyze the nature and type of web resources and studies the various standards for web citations.

All the previous literature are displayed that the researcher mostly used Web of Science & Scopus database for collecting data of any kind of metrics study and research growth analysis. The present study is a further extension of the previous works, attempting to evaluate the 100 years growth of LIS research using the Lens database.

3. The Lens

Lens (<https://www.lens.org/>) serves as the global patent and scholarly knowledge as a public good to inform science and technology-enabled problem-solving. Lens is an open global cyberinfrastructure to make the innovation system more efficient and fairer, more transparent and inclusive. It indexes nearly all of the global patent data integrated with scholarly literature and facilitates the same as open, a notable digital public good thus offering open mapping of the world of knowledge-directed innovation. It aims to enable more people to make better decisions, informed by evidence and inspired by imagination. The Lens enables cartography of the innovation landscape, allowing navigation from an idea to a product (or service) and back again. This makes producing new value in society quicker and more affordable. The lens creates transparency in the patent system, and to serve the public worldwide as a platform to explore, understand and improve its impact on society. The Lens informatics tools can assist the user to determine the boundaries of intellectual property constraints on deliverable innovations, and usable building blocks for future innovations.

4. Study Objectives

The main objectives of the study are to,

- 1) Reveal the present status of research productivity of the global scholarly LIS literature.
- 2) Identify top ten LIS publications attaining highest scholarly citations.
- 3) Examine the prominence of LIS publications in worldwide patents.
- 4) Identify top LIS publications claiming highest patent citations.
- 5) Examine the number of citing patents in scholarly LIS publications
- 6) Identify prominent contributors including top institution, country, authors, publishers, publications, etc.
- 7) Examine the OA status of scholarly LIS research in terms of degree of access/usage freedom expressed universally by OA Colour and CC Licenses.
- 8) Evaluate the decadal RGR and Doubling time of scholarly LIS publications ranging from May 1920 to April 2020.

5. Scope of the Study

The present study focuses on the growth and trends in LIS literature, authorship pattern, journal coverage, institutions involved in active research etc in between the date range, April 1920 to April 2020 (i.e. 100 Years). Citation studies are recognized as an indicator of the influence of published work on the scientific community. This study attempts to analyse the performance of LIS research output in terms of its content and coverage, growth rates, areas of research concentration, author productivity, and authorship pattern, journals and articles and other means of assisting the peer-review procedure. Performance of research institutions in the promotion of LIS research is also given due emphasis. In this study, the scope of LIS publication is not concentrated on the core LIS field. The Lens provides two way of exploring the scholarly LIS literature, one only the core LIS literature and another in addition to its multidisciplinary and cross-disciplinary field which related to LIS e.g. Information Theory. The decadal relative growth rate (RGR) and the doubling time estimation are also prominent in this paper. Concerning such a comprehensive study, data from the LIS research output originating from countries around the world were mined from the big data source – “the Lens”.

6. Design/ Methodology/ Approach

This study was based on data mining from the Lens database and subsequent analysis of data using spreadsheet software for enhanced visualization. Here the search was made through specifying the subject field “Library and Information Science”, and date range: April 1920 to April 2020. As the present study covers LIS publications with its multidisciplinary and cross-disciplinary field also which related to LIS, the recall of the result dataset may increase but the precision of the result decreases some extent. For this reason, after extracted the raw data, thorough data mining is made to understand the arrangement and correlation between different variables of the dataset. The search strategy deployed was started first from “Our Apps” in the homepage of the Lens and the selecting Scholar (Search and Analysis) a new window with New Scholar Search opened up. Following two screen-shots (*Figure 1 & 2*) indicates the further search strategies,

Figure 1 & 2: Screenshot of LENS Search Strategy

Again, for the purpose of evaluate the decadal relative growth rate and doubling time the formula, $RGR = \frac{LN(P2)-LN(P1)}{T2-T1}$ and $Dt = \frac{0.693}{RGR}$ are used respectively.

7. Results and Discussion

Table 1: Worldwide Status of LIS Literature

Works in Set	Works Cited by Patents	Patent Citations	Works Cited by Scholarly	Scholarly Citations
237820	4055	27864	110058	2503833

The total data sets retrieved from the Lens database comprise 237820 scholarly works in the discipline of Library and Information Science out of which 4055 (1.71 %) works have been cited by patents which in-turn received 27864 patent citations (6.87 patent citations/paper) while 110058 (46.28%) works were received 2503833 scholarly citations (22.75 scholarly citations/paper). (see Table 1)

7.1. Citing Patents:

General notion could be that researches/researchers in LIS have no direct referring of the patents, but table below provides strong evidence that patents are considered as a valuable information source contributing in the production of scholarly research in LIS.

Document Types	Granted Patents	Patent Application	Search Report	Unknown	Amended Patent	Limited Patent	Abstract
Total	13718	3505	885	482	70	6	1

It is also pertinent to note that the corpus comprising total LIS research publications (i.e. 237820) have cited 18667 patents including Granted Patent (73.49%), Patent Application(18.78%), and Search Report (4.74%). Thus, granted patents have been cited more in LIS literature than any other documents types pertaining to patents. (see Table 2)

7.1.1. Top 10 Citing Applicants and Citing Jurisdictions

SN	3A. Top 10 Citing Applicants	SN	3B. Top 10 Citing Jurisdictions
1	IBM	696	1 USA
2	Microsoft Corp	642	2 WIPO
3	Qualcomm Inc	454	3 EPO
4	Samsung Electronics Co Ltd	382	4 China
5	Huawei Tech Co Ltd	271	5 Germany
6	Errison Telefon Ab L M	269	6 France
7	Google Inc	258	7 Japan
8	Apple	240	8 South Korea
9	Broadcom Corp	190	9 Great Britain
10	Panasonic Corp	185	10 Australia
Total (Top 10)		3587	Total (Top 10)
Contribution to total Citing Patents		19.22%	Contribution to total Citing Patents
			98.26%

The top 10 patent applicants, including Microsoft Corp, IBM, Google, etc., are found to cover 19.22% of the total number of patents cited. At the same time, the top 10 citing jurisdictions occupy 98.26%, i.e. almost the entire area of citing patent. (see Table 3A & 3B)

7.2. Top Publications in terms of Citation Count:

The research value of a particular publication and its acceptance among researchers, citations count is the best way to determine. The top 10 scholarly publications are identified in terms of citation count, and the citations may be received either from scholarly works or from patents. Tables 4 and 5 displays the status of top 10 publications in terms of scholarly citations (see Table 4) and patent citations (see Table 5).

7.2.1. Top 10 Publications according to Scholarly Citations

S N	Title	Author	Journal Name	YoP	Scholarly Citations	Patent Citations	OA Status
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1	Robust uncertainty principles: exact signal reconstruction from highly incomplete frequency information	Emmanuel J Candes, Justin Romberg, Terence Tao	IEEE Transactions on Information Theory	2006	11927	200	OA
2	Cooperative diversity in wireless networks: Efficient protocols and outage behavior	J N Laneman, David Tse, Gregory W Wornell	do	2004	11286	83	NOA
3	New Directions in Cryptography	Whitfield Diffie, Martin E Hellman	do	1976	11028	359	OA
4	The capacity of wireless networks	Piyush Gupta, P R Kumar	do	2000	7854	47	OA
5	Least squares quantization in PCM	S P Lloyd	do	1982	7727	117	OA
6	Information Systems Success: The Quest for the Dependent Variable	William H DeLone, Ephraim R McLean	Information Systems Research	1992	7389	1	OA
7	De-noising by soft-thresholding	David L Donoho	IEEE Transactions on Information Theory	1995	7378	112	OA
8	Network information flow	Rudolf Ahlswede, Ning Cai, Shuo-Yen Robert Li, Raymond W Yeung	do	2000	7016	102	NOA
9	Space-time codes for high data rate wireless communication: performance criterion and code construction	Vahid Tarokh, Nambirajan Seshadri, A R Calderbank	do	1998	6804	250	OA
10	Term-weighting approaches in automatic text retrieval	Gerard Salton, Chris Buckley	Information Processing and Management	1988	6728	0	NOA
Total Scholarly Citations as covered by the Top 10 Publications					85137		

Table 4 above reveals the overall status of top 10 publications in LIS in terms of scholarly citation count. It may be noted here that “*IEEE Transactions on Information Theory*” is the journal which acquire the maximum articles in the top 10 list, which may not be a part of core LIS journals finds the reputed place

with linkage the LIS discipline owing to its multidisciplinary & cross-disciplinary nature particularly owing to its coverage of the field “information theory”. The paper entitled “*Robust uncertainty principles: exact signal reconstruction from highly incomplete frequency information*” authored by Emmanuel J Candes, Justin Romberg and Terence Tao published in 2006 received the highest scholarly citations i.e., 11927 while accounting for 200 patent citations. The total number of patents gained by these highly influential papers were 1387. The year of publication (YoP) of the articles ranges from 1967 to 2006. It is also interesting to note that 70% of these top 10 papers is available as open access (OA). Again, these top 10 publications cover 3.40% of total scholarly citations received by scholarly LIS literature (= 2503833 scholarly citations).

7.2.2. Top 10 Publications according to Patent Citations

SN	Title	Author	Journal Name	YoP	Patent Citations	Scholarly Citations	OA Status
1	A universal algorithm for sequential data compression	J Ziv, A Lempel	IEEE Transactions on Information Theory	1977	434	4335	OA
2	Good error-correcting codes based on very sparse matrices	David J C MacKay	do	1997	422	3185	OA
3	Optimal decoding of linear codes for minimizing symbol error rate (Corresp.)	Lalit R Bahl, John Cocke, Frederick Jelinek, J Raviv	do	1974	416	4521	OA
4	New Directions in Cryptography	Whitfield Diffie, Martin E Hellman	do	1976	359	11044	OA
5	Limited feedback unitary precoding for spatial multiplexing systems	David J Love, Robert W Heath	do	2005	315	721	NOA
6	Space-time block codes from orthogonal designs	Vahid Tarokh, Hamid Jafarkhani, A R Calderbank	do	1999	293	6478	NOA
7	Maximum-likelihood sequence estimation of digital sequences in the presence of intersymbol interference	G Forney	do	1972	272	2278	OA

8	Space-time codes for high data rate wireless communication: performance criterion and code construction	Vahid Tarokh , Nambirajan Seshadri, A R Calderbank	do	1988	250	6807	OA
9	Factor graphs and the sum-product algorithm	Frank R Kschischang , Brendan J Frey, Hans-Andrea Loeliger	do	2001	247	5044	OA
10	Iterative decoding of binary block and convolutional codes	Joachim Hagenau, E Offer, L Papke	do	1996	235	2171	OA
Total Patent Citations as covered by the Top 10 Publications					3243		

Table 5 above indicates the overall status of the top 10 publications in LIS in terms of patent citation count. As of in the case of top 10 publications according to scholarly citations, IEEE Transactions on Information Theory is the only journal which figures in the top 10 list, which may not be considered as one of the core but finds a reputed place in the discipline of Engineering though but connected with the LIS domain owing to its multidisciplinary & cross-disciplinary nature and its coverage of “information theory”. The paper entitled “*A universal algorithm for sequential data compression*” authored by J Ziv and A Lempel published in 1977 received the highest patent citations i.e., 434 while accounting for 4335 scholarly citations. The total number of patent citations gained by these highly influential papers were 3243. The year of publication (YoP) of the articles ranges from 1972 to 2005. It is also interesting to note that 80% of these top 10 papers is available as open access (OA). Again these top 10 publications cover 11.64% of total Patent citations received by scholarly LIS literature (=27864 patent citations).

7.3. Institution Wise Distribution:

The following Table 6 presents the name of top 10 institutions in terms of the total number of scholarly publications published by the institutions’ faculty, researcher/student either directly or by institutional funding. The researchers affiliated to “*The University of Illinois*” produced maximum number 1149 publications followed by the University of Information Professional or “*el profesional de la información universitaria*” (1052 publications) followed by “*University of Michigan*” with 967 publications. The total research productivity of these top institutions in the discipline of LIS collectively was found to be 7383.

S N	Name of the Institution	Total Publications	Scholarly	Percentage (%)
1	University of Illinois at Urbana–Champaign	1149		15.56
2	El profesional de la información	1052		14.25
3	University of Michigan	720		9.75
4	University of Sheffield	675		9.14
5	University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill	663		8.98
6	Rutgers University	651		8.82

7	University of Maryland, College Park	637	8.63
8	Stanford University	621	8.41
9	University of Texas at Austin	613	8.31
10	Pennsylvania State University	602	8.15
Total		7383	100

Institutions/Country Region Wise Distribution:

Table 7 shows country/region wise distributions of scholarly LIS publications. As already discussed, the University of Illinois is the top institution cover the highest number of scholarly LIS publications and its country/region United State also covers the maximum number of scholarly LIS publications (i.e. 41155). Again, it is important to note that these top 10 institutions countries/regions cover almost 31.08% of total LIS scholarly publications.

Table 7: Top 10 Institution Country/Region of Scholarly LIS Publications			
SN	Institution Country/Region	Total Scholarly Publications	Percentage (%)
1	United States	41155	55.68
2	United Kingdom	10627	14.38
3	China	4935	6.68
4	Canada	4011	5.43
5	Australia	3102	4.20
6	Spain	2848	3.85
7	Germany	2258	3.05
8	Netherlands	1803	2.44
9	India	1706	2.31
10	Brazil	1465	1.98
Total		73910	100

7.4. Author wise Distribution:

Some authors are found to be contributing to the LIS research output significantly enhancing the value of the discipline of LIS to a great extent. According to the following Table 8, H Askew is the topmost contributing author in the LIS field with almost 852 scholarly publications followed by Edward Bensley & James Seton-Anderson with 606 & 444 publications respectively. ALA & Haworth in the list of top 10 authors are not a single individual but an organization and does not represent an author as such. Interestingly only 2.75% of total LIS publications covered by top 10 authors of this field.

Table 8: Top 10 Authors of Scholarly LIS Publications			
SN	Name of the Author	Total Scholarly Publications	Percentage (%)
1	ALA*	2312	33.53
2	H. Askew	852	12.35
3	Haworth *	762	11.05
4	Edwars Bensly	606	8.79
5	James Seton-Anderson	444	6.44
6	J. Ardagh	408	5.91

7	Archibald Sparke	404	5.86
8	John B Wainwright	376	5.45
9	Edward J G Forse	366	5.31
10	M H Dodds	366	5.31
Total		6896	100

* It may be noted that these are not individuals but represent associations.

7.5. Distribution according to Publication Types:

Considering the distribution of scholarly LIS publications there are mainly 4 types of publications viz. journal article, conference proceedings, book chapter & books. Among these four journals, article covers the maximum portion (= 97.78%) of publications and far from the rest of the publication type. Conference proceedings, book chapter & books are closely follows each other with 2645, 1273& 1203 publications respectively. (see Table 9)

SN	Publication Type	Total Scholarly Publications	Percentage (%)
1	Journal Articles	232488	97.78
2	Conference Proceedings	2645	1.11
3	Book Chapters	1273	0.53
4	Book	1203	0.51
5	Journal Issue	184	0.08
6	Editorial	20	0.01
7	Dataset	3	0.001
8	Other	2	0.001
9	Letter	1	~0
10	Unknown	1	~0
Total		237820	100

7.6. Journals wise Distributions:

Table 10 brings out distribution of scholarly LIS publications among top 10 journals. Notes and Queries, IEEE Transactions on Information Theory and Notes are top 3 journals with 48372, 13961 & 11149 publications respectively. Notes and Queries is a long-running (1849-present) quarterly scholarly journal that publishes short articles related to English language and literature, lexicography, history, and scholarly antiquarianism; published by Oxford University Press (OUP, UK). Again, IEEE Transactions on Information Theory is not a core LIS journal but related with information theory with its multidisciplinary & cross-disciplinary nature. Again, it is important to note that top 10 journals of scholarly LIS publications cover almost 44.93 % of total LIS publications.

SN	Journal Name	Total Scholarly Publications	Percentage (%)
1	Notes and Queries	48372	45.27
2	IEEE Transactions on Information Theory	13961	13.06

3	Notes	11149	10.43
4	College & Research Libraries News	6680	6.25
5	College & Research Libraries	6293	5.90
6	Scientometrics	5431	5.08
7	Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling	4770	4.46
8	The Library Quarterly	3987	3.73
9	The Papers of the Bibliographical Society of America	3177	2.97
10	Library Review	3043	2.85
Total		106863	100

7.7. Conference wise Distribution:

Table 11 below displays the distribution of scholarly LIS literature among top 10 conferences. Association for Information Science and Technology, International Symposium on Information Theory and Language Resources and Evaluation are top 3 conferences with 618, 477 & 423 publications respectively. The Association for Information Science and Technology (ASIS&T) is a non-profit membership organization (from 1937) for information professionals that sponsors an annual conference as well as several serial publications, including the JAsIST. Again, it is important to note that top 10 conferences of scholarly LIS publications covers only 1.08% of total LIS publications.

SN	Conference Name	Scholarly Publications	Percentage
1	Association for Information Science and Technology	618	24.16
2	International Symposium on Information Theory	477	18.65
3	Language Resources and Evaluation	423	16.54
4	Data Mining in Bioinformatics	385	15.05
5	Information Wissenschaft & Praxis	296	11.57
6	Aslib Journal of Information Management	272	10.63
7	ACM Conference on Hypertext	31	1.21
8	Web Science	20	0.79
9	International Conference on Electronic Publishing	18	0.70
10	Text REtrieval Conference	18	0.70
Total		2558	100

7.8. Publisher wise Distribution:

In the case of publisher wise distribution of scholarly LIS publications, Oxford University Press (OUP) suppress the rest of the publisher to a large margin. Out of the 160501 publications covered under top 10 publishers, OUP covers almost 30.07%, which is 20.29 % of total LIS publications. Emerald and

Routledge publications are in second and third position with 26047 & 22937 publications respectively. Again 67.49% of total LIS publications covered by the top 10 publishers. (see Table 12)

SN	Publisher Name	Total Scholarly Publications	Percentage (%)
1	Oxford University Press (OUP)	48261	30.07
2	Emerald Group Publishing Ltd.	26047	16.23
3	Routledge	22937	14.29
4	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Inc.	13450	8.38
5	Music Library Association	11153	6.95
6	Taylor and Francis Ltd.	9626	6.00
7	Association of College and Research Libraries	9107	5.67
8	Springer Netherlands	6840	4.26
9	Elsevier Limited	6688	4.17
10	American Library Association	6392	3.98
Total		160501	100

7.9. OA Status of Global LIS Publications:

There are many types of open access, perhaps because it is such a young movement that it's still developing standards. According to SHERPA/RoMEO (2020), journal publishers are classified into four basic types and which indicates by four different colours, viz. Green, Blue, Yellow and White. Again OA policy also uses some license (*Creative Common License*) for valid distribution of publications under OA but with some terms and conditions. In the present study, the Lens database categorized the OA status of the scholarly LIS publications into two different way, viz. according to OA Colour and according to OA License.

7.9.1. OA Status according to Open Access Colour

SN	Open Access Colour	Total Scholarly Publications	Percentage
1	Green	17832	31.64%
2	Gold	17238	30.60%
3	Bronze	15362	27.26%
4	Hybrid	4963	8.81%
5	Unknown	951	1.70%
Total		56346	100%

In the case of OA Colour, the distribution of scholarly LIS publications has four basic types with colour code Green, Gold, Bronze & Hybrid. There are also some OA journals owning no OA colour. In the case of OA publications by colour, Green OA covers the highest number of publications i.e. 17832, closely followed by Gold and Bronze OA with 17238 & 15362 publications respectively. Again, 4963 publications cover under Hybrid OA policy and 951 number of OA publications don't refer any OA

colour. The total number of publications covers under OA colour obtain 23.69% of total scholarly LIS publications. However, Lens does not categorizes research publications into other prevalent OA colours such as Blue, Yellow, White, Diamond and Platinum. (see Table 13)

7.9.2. OA Status according to Open Access License

In the case of CC licenses, one aspect is important to note that CC0 and PDM differ in important respects and have distinct purposes. CC0 (No Rights Reserved) can only be used by the original creator of a work and PDM (No Known Copyright) anyone who wants (Creative Commons, 2016).

SN	License Type	Total Scholarly Publications	Percentage
1	Unknown	33423	59.51%
2	CC BY	10064	17.92%
3	CC BY-NC	6643	11.83%
4	CC BY-NC-ND	2662	4.74%
5	CC BY-NC-SA	1796	3.20%
6	CC BY-SA	891	1.59%
7	CC0	189	0.34%
8	Publisher Specific	170	0.30%
9	Public Domain	163	0.29%
10	ACS Specific	157	0.28%
Total		56158	100%

Table 14 above indicates the result of the OA status of the present study according to several OA licenses. OA publications without any known license covers the highest percentage (59.51%) and OA publications with CC BY (17.92%) and CC BY-NC (11.83%) are in second and third position respectively. The total number of publications covers under OA license obtain 23.61% of total scholarly LIS publications which is slightly lower than covered by OA colour.

7.10. Decadal Relative Growth Rate (RGR) & Doubling Time (Dt):

The present research covers the development of LIS literature over a full century (i.e. 1920-2020). The Relative Growth Rate explains the increase in the number of publications of LIS research output during different periods. The growth of publications was analysed by using two parameters Relative Growth Rate and Doubling time (Mahapatra, 1985). RGR is a measure to study the increase in the number of publications of time. It is calculated as,

$$RGR = \frac{LN(P2) - LN(P1)}{T2 - T1}$$

Where,

P2 and P1 are the cumulative number of publications in the year's T2 and T1;

P1= LogP1 (Natural log of initial number of publication);

P2=LogP2 (Natural log of final number of publication).

Doubling time is the time required for publications to become double of the existing amount. It is directly related to RGR and is defined as the time required for the articles to become two-fold of the existing amount. If the number of articles in subject doubles during a given period, then difference between logarithms of numbers at the end of this period must be the logarithm of the number 2. In this study

Napier logarithm is used, and the taken value of \log_2 is 0.693. Hence, as per this (0.693), an average growth rate we calculated by what time interval the Napier logarithm of numbers does increase by 0.693 (Basavraja, Vinay & Kori, 2019). So the Doubling time is calculated using the following formula:

$$Dt = \frac{0.693}{RGR}$$

Where,

Dt= Doubling time

RGR= Relative Growth Rate

S N	Decade	Publication Count	Cumulative Publication Count	LN(P1)	LN(P2)	Decadal RGR	Mean RGR R _t (P)	D _t (P)	Mean D _t (P)
1	May. 1920- Apr. 1930	11752	11752	9.37	-	0	1.57	0	0.492
2	May. 1930- Apr. 1940	12442	24194	9.43	10.09	0.72		0.963	
3	May. 1940- Apr. 1950	8681	32875	9.07	10.40	0.97		0.714	
4	May. 1950- Apr. 1960	7724	40599	8.95	10.61	1.66		0.417	
5	May. 1960- Apr. 1970	9154	49753	9.12	10.81	1.86		0.373	
6	May. 1970- Apr. 1980	9985	59738	9.21	11.00	1.88		0.369	
7	May. 1980- Apr. 1990	17608	77346	9.78	11.26	2.05		0.338	
8	May. 1990- Apr. 2000	27481	104827	10.22	11.56	1.78		0.389	
9	May. 2000- Apr. 2010	54745	159572	10.91	11.98	1.76		0.394	
10	May. 2010 - Apr. 2020	78104	237676	11.27	12.38	1.47		0.471	

The Table 15 outlines the status of decadal RGR and the doubling time of the scholarly LIS research ranging from May 1920 to April 2020. The result of the study indicates that the decadal RGR and doubling time of scholarly LIS literature is not constant, rather it shows an up & down in growth curve. May 1930-April 1940 Decade has the lowest decadal RGR value (= 0.72) consecutively the highest doubling time value (= 0.963). Reversely, May 1980-April 1990 Decade has the highest decadal RGR value (= 2.05) consecutively the lowest doubling time value (= 0.338). The average value of the decadal RGR and the doubling time is 15.7 and 0.492 respectively. Following figures shows the graphical representations of decadal growth of LIS literature ranging from May 1920 to April 2020:

Figure 3: Decadal Growth rate of Works in Set

As shown in the Figure 3 above, in the case of “Works in Set”, except for the third & fourth decade i.e. 1940-1960, the work in LIS literature has increased every decade since the previous decade.

Figure 4: Decadal Growth rate of Citing patents

The Figure 4 above displays the growth trend of Citing Patents in LIS literature over the past 10 decades. The plot indicates that the growth of citing patents doesn’t follow any fixed pattern but it decreased unexpectedly in the last decade i.e. 2010-2020.

Figure 5: Decadal Growth rate of Work Cited by Patents vs. Patent Citations

Above Figure 5 indicates that in the case of both “work cited by patent” and “patent citations”, the value increases after the third decade and declines again over the last decade, i.e. 2010-2020. Similarly, the Figure 6 below displays the comparative plot of “works cited by scholarly” and “scholarly citations”. Similar to Figure 5, it only decreased over the last decade, i.e. 2010-2020, but continued to increase in first 9 decades i.e. from 1920 to 2010.

Figure 6: Decadal Growth Rate of Work Cited by Scholarly vs. Scholarly Citations

8. Summary & Conclusion

The present study demonstrated some general inferences on the basic scientometric attributes like scholarly citations, patent citations, citing patents, coverage of top 10 authors, publishers, articles, journals, conferences etc of the scholarly research collaboration of the LIS literature. The LIS data

included 237820 papers with 4055 (1.71 %) works received patent citations. The average scholarly citations received by 110058 (46.28%) works were found to be 22.75 cites/paper. 18667 patents found mention in the overall LIS research with granted patents gained prominence (73.49%) followed by patent application (18.78%). “IEEE Transactions on Information Theory” turned out to be the most prominent and preferred journal of LIS research while Oxford University Press (OUP) was the top-ranked journal followed by Emerald and Routledge. “Notes and Queries”, “IEEE Transactions on Information Theory” and “Notes” were the top 3 journals and “Association for Information Science and Technology” (ASIS&T), “International Symposium on Information Theory” and “Language Resources and Evaluation” emerged the top 3 conferences. The OA status, decadal RGR and doubling time also important aspects of the study. Green OA had 17832 papers, closely followed by Gold and Bronze OA with 17238 & 15362 publications respectively. OA publications without CC license were maximum (59.51%) with CC BY (17.92%) and CC BY-NC (11.83%) publications. LIS research adhering to CC license was 23.61% of total scholarly LIS publications. In the case of decadal RGR & doubling time, May 1930-April 1940 Decade has the lowest decadal RGR value (= 0.72) consecutively the highest doubling time value (= 0.963); reversely, May 1980-April 1990 Decade has the highest decadal RGR value (= 2.05) consecutively the lowest doubling time value (= 0.338). Library and Information Science (LIS) is a field of social sciences and it’s not common for scholarly publications in this area to be applied for in a patent. Additionally, many of the LIS scholarly literature cited several patents to increase its research value. With its multidisciplinary nature, LIS publications can easily fit into other discipline and made a significant addition to the knowledge society.

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